

Investigating Interlayer Bonding and Defect Analysis in Roller-Compaction-Assisted Core–Shell Structured Additively Manufactured Composites

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Celebrating 50 Years

- › Additive manufacturing process
- › Research gaps
- › Experimental setup
- › Methodology
- › Experimental analysis
- › Conclusions

Current challenges:

- Low fiber volume fraction
- High void content
- Weak interlayer bonding

- Replicate the printing process for controlled impregnation & core shell formation.
- Quantitatively apply roller assisted compaction pressure.
- Investigate the void fraction, FVF and SBS.

Introduction- Experimental Setup

Introduction- Experimental Setup

- (1) Fiber Spool
- (2) Alignment
- (3) Impregnator bath
- (4) Metering
- (5) UV setup
- (6) Linear guide
- (7) Compaction roller
- (8) Pneumatic cylinder
- (9) Take-up mandrel

Dry Fiber: Hexcel IM7 unsized 12K tow

Resin: FibreGlast 4600 epoxy + FibreGlast 4690 hardener + Liqcreate Tough-x photopolymeric

Sample Collection & Specimen Extraction

ILSS

$L = 6T$
 $W = 2T$
 $T = 3 \text{ to } 4 \text{ mm}$

MicroCT

$L = \sim 5 \text{ mm}$
 $W = \sim 15 \text{ mm}$
 $T = 3 \text{ to } 4 \text{ mm}$

Confocal

$W = 11 \text{ mm}$
 $T = 2.5 \text{ mm}$

- › CT Scanner: Bruker 1172 scanner (USA).
- › Voltage ~40 kV, current 250 μ A, frame averaging: 4 images per projection at a field of view of 4000 \times 2664 pixels with a pixel size of 6 μ m.
- › Reconstruction: NRecon (Micro Photonics Inc., USA) and
- › Image analysis: Dragonfly (Comet Yxlon, Germany).

Methodology: FVF Calculation

Discretization sensitivity

$$\text{Void fraction} = \frac{\text{Void area (Color Coded)}}{\text{Total Area}}$$

From MicroCT analysis

3D Rendering of Voids-Volume

UV0_P0

UV0_P100

UV0_P200

Force-Displacement Curves

Short Beam Strength: ASTM D2344

$$SBS = \frac{0.75P_{max}}{bh}$$

